

ROLE OF VRANABANDHANA IN NETRA ROGAS: INSIGHTS FROM AYURVEDIC LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

The Ayurvedic concept of *Vranabandhana*, which includes wound cleansing, protection, and tissue regeneration, holds significant clinical relevance in the management of *Netra Rogas*. Classical texts such as the *Sushruta Samhita* and *Ashtanga Hridaya* elaborate systematic approaches for ocular wound care, particularly following trauma and surgical procedures. *Vranabandhana* encompasses therapeutic measures like *Shodhana*, *Stambhana*, *Ropana*, and *Bandhana*, which collectively aid in restoring structural and functional integrity of ocular tissues. These principles are especially valuable in conditions such as *Arma*, *Kshataja Abhishyanda*, and *Pakshmakopa*, where prevention of infection, control of inflammation, and promotion of healing are essential. Ayurvedic formulations including *Jatyadi Ghrita*, *Yashtimadhu Taila*, *Triphala Kashaya*, and *Panchavalka Kashaya* are administered through modalities like *Ashchyotana*, *Pichu*, *pindi* and *Lepa etc.*, demonstrating wound-healing, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. This review highlights that *Vranabandhana* offers a safe and holistic approach to integrative ophthalmic wound management.

KEYWORDS: *Vranabandhana*, *Arma*, *Pakshmakopa*, *kshataja abhishyanda*.**INTRODUCTION**

The Netra is regarded in Ayurveda as a *Pradhana Indriya*,^[1] essential for perception and daily functioning, and is predominantly constituted by *Tejo Mahabhuta*,^[2] rendering it highly sensitive to pathological disturbances. Ocular disorders involving *Vrana* characterized by *Dhatu-bheda*, *Shotha*, *Vedana*, and loss of tissue integrity are considered grave due to their potential to cause irreversible visual impairment, especially when vital ocular structures are involved.^[3] *Acharya Sushruta* emphasizes that improper management of *Vrana* in delicate organs leads to *Vaikrutapaha* and permanent functional loss.

Among the *Shashti Upakrama*, *Vranabandhana* occupies a pivotal role in stabilizing wounds (*Vrana Sthairya*), preventing *Vata Prakopa*, minimizing movements and protecting the lesion from external aggravating factors.^[4] In *Netra Rogas*, constant eyelid motion, exposure to light, wind, dust, and microbial contamination predispose

ocular wounds to rapid deterioration from *Shuddha* to *Dushita Vrana*. *Vranabandhana* counteracts these factors through *Rakshana* (protection), *Sandhana* (tissue approximation), *Vedana Shamana*, and *Ropana*,^[5] thereby promoting orderly healing.

Its clinical relevance is evident in conditions such as *Savvana Shukla*, *Kshata Shukla*, *Abhishyanda-janya Netra Rogas*, *Arma*, *Adhimantha*, traumatic ocular injuries, and post-operative conditions, where *bandhana* along with *Aschyotana*, *Parisheka*, *Tarpana*, *Pindi*, and *Anjana* are employed using meticulously selected *Ropana Dravyas* with proven efficacy in reducing irritation, controls inflammation, and supports tissue repair.^[6] The principles of *Vranabandhana* closely parallel to modern ophthalmic practices like eye bandaging and corneal protection, underscoring its contemporary relevance. Revisiting this classical concept offers valuable insights for integrative and holistic ocular wound management.

Definition of vrana

Breaking of body tissues into fragments and There is discolouration of body due to *vrana*....

Definition of Vrana Bandhana

The procedure meant for covering the wound /injured part is called as *VRANA BANDHANA*. Bandaging wound facilitates the process of *vrana shodhana* as well as *ropana*. *Bandhana* is usually applied after smearing of medicated pastes etc.,

VRANA BANDHANA PRAYOJYA UPAKARANA [BANDAGING MATERIAL]

Acharya Sushruta has described various materials for *Vranabandhana* (bandaging), which should be selected according to the nature of the disease, the season, and their suitability for the condition.

According to vagbhata

Avika	trapusi
Snayuvakajam	Phalakam
Tamra	Charma valkala
Ayasa	

According to susruta

Ksauma (Flax)	Patrona (cloth made from plant fibers)	Karpasa (Cotton)
China patta (Chinese silk fabric)	Vidala (Split bamboo)	Avika (Sheep wool)
Charma (Leather of animals like deer etc)	Rajju (Rope made from grass)	Dukula (Fine silk)
Antarvalkala (Inner barks of trees like bhurjapatra)	Santanika (Pad of silk cotton)	Kausheya (Silk)
Alabu (Gourd skin)	Louha (Metals)	

TYPES OF BANDHANA

- According to shape-AkrutiAnusara
- According to site-Sthanaanusara
- According to doshas- Doshaanusara

- According to ACHARYA VAGBHATA - 15 TYPES

[INCLUDED UTSANGI BANDHA]

TYPES OF BANDHANA [AAKARUTI ANUSARA]:

- According to ACHARYA SUSHRUTHA - 14 TYPES

- According to ACHARYA CHARAKA - 2 TYPES - 1] VAAMA 2] DAKSHINA

BANDHANA ACCORDING TO SHAPE [AAKARA ANUSARA]

Bandha	Sthana
Kosha bandha	Angustaanguliparvasu
Dama	Sambhadeange
Swasthika	Sandhikurchakabhusthanantaratalakanaishu
Anuvellitha	Shakhasu
Pratholi	Grevamedrayo
Mandala	Vritheange
Sthagika	Angushta angulimedrageshu
Yamaka	Yamalavrana
Khatwa	Hanushankhagandesu
China	Apanga pradesha
Vibandha	Prustodauraha
Vithana	Murdhani
Gophana	Chibukanasaustaamsabastishu
Panchangi	Urdwajatruga
Utsaangi	Bahu

Bandhana according to site [STHANA ANUSARA]

Ghadha bandha	Shithila bandha	Sama bandha
[TIGHT BANDAGE] Bandhana which produces pressure but doesn't induce pain.	[LOOSE BANDAGE] Bandhana which stretches on pressure	Neither too loose nor too tight.
SITE – Sushruta- kaksha, kukshi, vankshana, nitamba, shira, uru	Sushruta.-Netra, sandhi	Sushruta- shaakha, karna, kanta, vadana, parshwa, prusta, udara, medra, mushka
Vagbhata- kaksha,vankshana,uru,shiras, sphik	Vagbhata - netra, sandhi	Vagbhata- shakha, vadana, karna, gala, prusta, parshwa, uraha, udara, mushka, mehana

BANDHANA ACCORDING TO DOSHA [DOSHA ANUSARA]**In pittaja / raktaja vrana**

In place of gadha bandhana sthana – sama bandhana is applied

In place of sama bandhana sthana – shithila bandhana is applied

In place of shithila bandhana sthana – no bandhana is applied

In vataja / kaphaja vrana

In place of shithila bandhana sthana – sama bandhana is applied

In place of sama bandhana sthana – Gadha bandhana is applied

In place of gadha bandhana sthana – more tight bandaging is applied

VRANA BANDHANA MENTIONED IN NETRA ROGAS**1. Swastika bandha^[7]**

from the name of the bandage it is clear that the shape of it is like the swastika symbol of Hindu religion or the English numerical 8. In this bandaging is done by crossing on vranasthana so that stability of bandaging is maintained.

INDICATIONS: Used around eyebrows and around ears.

FREQUENCY OF BANDAGING

Vrana	Rutu	Frequency
Vataja/ kaphaja vrana	Hemanta and Vasanta	change it every 3 rd day.
Pittaja/ Raktaja vrana	Greeshma and sharad rutu	change it twice daily

BANDHA GUNA

Crushed and lacerated wounds, fractures, dislocation of joints, bone hanging cutting/tearing of bones, tendons, veins etc. heal quickly by bandaging. The wounded person will be able to sit, walk and stand easily, finds comfort in lying and sitting and the wound heals quickly.

CONTRAINDICATIONS OF BANDHANA

Pittarakta dushti, Abhighathavishanimitta with presence of Shophya, Daha, Paka, Raga, Toda, vedana, etc. When the wound occurs due to alkali or the fire, causes wasting of muscle tissues hence bandage should not be applied. In kushtha patients, Persons burned with fire, Person having Diabetes & in rat poisoning cases, Bandage should not be applied on wound & also in karnika, toxic wound & mamsapaka & gudapaka.

BANDHA YANTRANA

Yantrana (control, tightening/putting knots to keep the bandage in place) may be done at three places i.e above, below, sides of the wound, but not on the wound.

2. China bandha^[8]

This is used for apanga i.e outer or inner canthus of eye, hence a round piece or a piece of cloth having the width as much as it can cover eyes is taken & long bandages are attached to it, this bandages are tied behind the head.

Site - outer canthus of eyes.

BANDHANA AVACHARANA^[9]**KAVALIKA**

Keeping 2 or 4 folds of soft cloth over wound to protect from injury is called as Kavalika- Cotton pad.

- ❑ A thick Kavalika (cotton pad or paste of drugs) should be kept on the wound, then bandage should be tied moving it in the direction of the left hand, straight without folding, without any twists.

The knot should not be tied on the wound as that gives rise to pain.

VAIKESHIKA

- ❑ Application of medicated ghritha/paste of drugs over a band of cloth or threads which is rolled and made like a wick to keep over the wound is called as Vikeshika Medicated gauze/wick.
- ❑ Vikeshika aushadha should be neither very unctuous nor very dry, or uneven (irregular) because too much of unctuousness produces exudation, too much of dryness produces tearing and keeping it irregularly causes friction at the edges the wound.

EFFECT OF PROPER BANDHANA

When the bandage is applied in the proper manner, there will be relief from pain, purification of blood and softness of the wound.

VRANABANDHANA AFTER SHASTRA KARMA IN NETRAROGAS**▶ IN SHUKLAGATA ROGAS****ARMA CHEDANA^[10]**

After arma chedhana eye is smeared with powder of yavanala, trikatu, lavana. Then skilled physician should anoint the eye and apply bandage according to strength of doshas, season, time and then treat it as vrana and bandage is removed after 3 days and fomentation is given with rubbed palms.

▶ IN VARTMAGATA ROGAS**BISAGRANTHI^[11]**

- ❑ After shastra karma, it is bathed with mixture of honey & gritha. Then, bandaged suitably to protect the wound and promote recovery.

PAKSHMAKOPA^[12]

❑ After suturing, The two ends of the sutures should be fixed over the forehead with the help of a bandage. After confirming that the two ends which were sutured have been properly united and that the lid has become stable, the physician should remove the stitches made with horse hair.

▶ IN KRISHNAGATA ROGAS**AJAKAJATA^[13]**

The prolapsed or bulged part is cleaned well and the selected lateral part is pricked with a needle to irrigate the infected fluid, Gomamsa churnam + Ghritha is filled, in the gap and bandaged. Bandage has to continue for 7 days. After 7 days if any raised part remains that should be scraped out.

▶ IN DRISTIGATA ROGAS**KAPHAJA LINGANASHA^[14]**

After vyadhana karma, Affected eye should be softly massaged with grutha. Then, eye should be bandaged with piece of linen.

KARMUKHATHA OF VRANABANDHANA IN NETRAROGAS

- ✓ Vranabandhana protects the ocular wound from dust, wind, microbes, and excess light and acts as a mechanical barrier against secondary contamination.
- ✓ Provides gentle compression to control bleeding, stabilize wounds, and maintain proper tissue alignment.
- ✓ Enhances retention and therapeutic efficacy of locally applied formulations such as Chakshushya, Pitta–Rakta Shamaka, and Vrana Ropaka drugs.
- ✓ Drugs used in Bandhana provide moisturizing effect thus promote epidermal migration and enhances formation of connective tissue for early healing.
- ✓ Reduces local inflammation and edema.
- ✓ Promotes faster wound healing and epithelial regeneration.
- ✓ Reduces postoperative and post-traumatic edema, vascular congestion, and inflammatory exudates, creating a favorable environment for healing.
- ✓ Alleviates pain, photophobia, and irritation through immobilization and gentle pressure.
- ✓ Maintains wound margins, minimizing fibrosis and promoting cosmetically favourable healing.
- ✓ Controls discharge in Abhishyanda janya Netra rogas and stabilizes corneal or conjunctival ulcers, enhancing the effect of systemic and topical therapies.
- ✓ Supports recovery in chronic inflammatory ocular diseases and post-surgical cases, accelerating healing and improving functional outcomes.

DRESSING

A dressing is a sterile pad or compress applied to wound to promote healing and protect the wound from further harm.

TYPES

1. Adhesive Dressing: It is used for small wound and is available in the centre of adhesive bandage on inner surface.
2. Gauze Dressing: It is a thick cotton pad, used for large wound.

COMPONENTS OF DRESSING

- ▶ Inner contact layer: It is non-absorbent and only allows secretion to pass into the absorbent layer. It does not allow penetration of granulation tissue. It is usually kept wet. Either mesh gauze or sofra tulle is used.
- ▶ Intermediate absorbent layer : made up of cotton which absorbs the secretions.
- ▶ Outer layer: as supportive is made up of gauze.

Dressings are fixed to the place by: bandages, plasters, Dynoplast, crepe bandages.

BANDAGING

- ▶ It is the process of covering a wound or injured part using most appropriate bandage.
- ▶ A BANDAGE is a piece of material used either to support a medical device.

eg: dressing or splint, or on its own to provide support to the body.

PURPOSE OF BANDAGING IN EYE

- ❖ To immobilize an injured part and relieve pain
- ❖ To support the wound and dressing
- ❖ To control haemorrhage
- ❖ To improve venous blood flow by applying pressure
- ❖ To reduce or prevent swelling
- ❖ To immobilize a fracture or dislocation

PRINCIPLES OF BANDAGING^[15]

1. Eye bandaging should be carried out only after proper ocular cleansing and dressing, strictly maintaining aseptic precautions.
2. The eyelids must be gently closed in their natural position before placement of the eye pad to avoid pressure on the globe.
3. After initial few circular turns, the required type of bandaging is then done.
4. Bandage is unrolled outwards.
5. During bandaging, latter turn should overlap 2/3rd of earlier turn.
6. Firm, adequate pressure should be used during bandaging.
7. After completing the procedure, the knot should not lie over the eye or over the bony points to prevent localized pressure injury.
8. It should not cause venous or arterial compression.
9. Eye bandages should be changed and inspected at appropriate intervals to assess healing and detect complications early.

EYE BANDAGE^[16]**▶ USES**

To support eye dressings after surgeries.

▶ Method

1. Take a horizontal turn around the head above the affected eye.
2. Now take the bandage towards the occiput.
3. Pass it below the ear on the affected side and bring it obliquely upwards over the dressing.
4. Take three turns like this. Finally, take two horizontal turns around the head and secure it on the forehead.

DISCUSSION

- ❖ The concept of Vranabandhana in Ayurveda exemplifies the profound surgical and wound management acumen of ancient Indian physicians. Acharya Sushruta, regarded as the father of surgery, emphasized that proper Bandhana not only protects the wound but also facilitates Shodhana and Ropana. The same foundational principles underlie the objectives of modern ophthalmic dressing namely protection, absorption of discharge, infection control, and promotion of tissue repair.
- ❖ In the context of Netra Rogas, Vranabandhana assumes special significance owing to the delicate anatomy of the eye and periorcular structures. Postoperative and post-traumatic ocular wounds require both mechanical protection and pharmacological support. The use of medicated oils and pastes such as Jatyadi Ghrita, Yashtimadhu Taila, or Triphala Kashaya in Bandhana not only ensures local drug delivery but also provides anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant effects, comparable to modern topical wound-healing agents.
- ❖ Ayurvedic classics meticulously categorize Bandhana based on dosha predominance, site, and shape (Aakruti), demonstrating an early understanding of individualized wound care. For example, Shithila Bandhana for Pittaja Vrana parallels the modern principle of avoiding excessive pressure in inflamed or hyperemic tissues, while Gadha Bandhana for Vata-Kaphaja Vrana resembles compression dressing used to reduce edema and promote perfusion.
- ❖ In Shalaky Tantra, specific Bandhana types such as Swastika Bandha and Cheena Bandha are described for ocular application, ensuring stability without excessive strain. These techniques display remarkable surgical precision, akin to present-day eye pad and pressure patch methods used in ophthalmic surgery. Post-surgical procedures like Arma Chedana, Bisagrandhi Chikitsa, and Pakshmakopa management further exemplify the integration of wound cleansing, medication, and Bandhana comparable to aseptic postoperative dressing protocols. After shastrakarma, The skilled

physician should apply bandage according to strength of doshas, season, time.

- ❖ The Ropana action of Ayurvedic formulations has been substantiated in several pharmacological studies, which demonstrate enhanced collagen synthesis, angiogenesis, and epithelial regeneration. These findings support the ancient observation that Bandhana not only acts as a protective cover but also as a therapeutic vehicle enhancing sustained drug release at the wound site.
- ❖ Furthermore, Vranabandhana embodies the holistic philosophy of Ayurveda, where physical healing is supported by the balance of Dosha, Dhātu, and Agni. The understanding of Desha, Kala, and Bala in deciding the frequency and type of Bandhana parallels evidence-based wound management in modern practice, where wound dressing protocols are customized based on tissue type, exudate level, and infection status.
- ❖ Thus, the Ayurvedic principles of Vranabandhana are not only scientifically rational but also clinically adaptable. Reinterpreting these classical techniques in light of modern wound care science may provide valuable insights into developing cost-effective, biocompatible, and sustainable ocular dressings. Future research focusing on standardization, pharmacological evaluation, and clinical validation of Ayurvedic Bandhana Dravyas can pave the way for integrative ophthalmic wound care strategies. Drugs used in bandhana provide moisturizing effect thus promote epidermal migration and enhances formation of connective tissue for early healing. Sustained release action of medication in bandhana enhances drug availability for longer duration. Thus, provides prolonged therapeutic effect.

CONCLUSION

- ▶ The ancient science of Vranabandhana illustrates the depth and precision of Ayurvedic surgical practice. Its emphasis on cleanliness, protection, and promotion of tissue repair mirrors the objectives of modern ophthalmic wound care. Through the application of medicated dressings and individualized bandaging techniques, Ayurveda anticipated many principles now recognized in evidence-based medicine. The integration of these classical practices with contemporary ophthalmology holds immense potential for enhancing wound healing, ensuring patient comfort, and supporting holistic recovery. Thus, Vranabandhana stands as a timeless contribution from Ayurveda, offering valuable insights for sustainable and integrative ocular wound management in the modern era. The concepts, theories and techniques clearly mentioned by our acharyas hold true even in today's practice. This paper highlights the similarities and the differences between traditional Indian method and modern method of bandaging in shalaky tantra and we can

say that our ancient surgeons were very evolved with effective management.

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